

Accurate modelling of the bifacial gain potential of rooftop solar photovoltaic systems

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ABSTRACT

Bifacial solar modules have emerged as a promising technology in utility-scale photovoltaic systems, experiencing significant growth and capturing a substantial market share worldwide, as reported by the International Technology Roadmap for Photovoltaic (ITRPV) 2023. Despite this progress, the potential of bifacial modules in rooftop applications remains largely unexplored. This paper aims to address this knowledge gap by conducting a comprehensive study utilizing Monte Carlo Ray Tracing techniques coupled with detailed electrical modelling. The primary objective of this study is to investigate the viability of implementing bifacial solar modules on rooftops by examining the potential energy yield gains. By conducting a detailed analysis on a representative rooftop in Canberra, Australia, real-world conditions, and variations are incorporated, providing a more accurate assessment of the energy yield gains achievable in such settings. The simulation results reveal that the implementation of bifacial solar modules on rooftops within Australia can result in energy yield gains of up to 22.6%. These findings demonstrate the considerable potential of bifacial technology in maximizing solar energy production in rooftop applications. The analysis shows significant implications of module and system design on the potential gain. For example, electrical optimisation of individual modules in a system accounted for 1.4% of the bifacial gain. The analysis considers full annual time-step simulation, typical mechanical mounting components, installation orientations and module characteristics, ensuring practical relevance and reliability of the results.

1. Introduction

Solar photovoltaics (PV) has emerged as a transformative technology in the clean energy transition, playing a pivotal role in combating climate change. The rapid advancements in solar cell efficiency over the past decades have made PV the most cost-effective form of new electricity generation across many regions globally.

Rooftop PV installation will play an important role in this renewable energy transition. This has been recognized by many research publications assessing the potential of rooftop photovoltaics [1–6]. Moreover, the adoption of cool roofs, utilizing highly reflective rooftop materials, has seen continuous growth in market share, contributing to increasing building thermal performance [7–11].

One of the promising technological developments in PV technologies is the recent industrialisation of bifacial solar module manufacturing. According to the ITRPV 2023 report, bifacial modules have gained

popularity and are expected to occupy a significant share of the PV market [12]. Bifacial PV modules are capable of capturing sunlight from both the front and back, offering the potential for increased energy gain compared to traditional monofacial modules. However, most of the existing research on the benefits of bifacial modules has focused on large, ground-mounted PV installations [13–16], with relatively little investigation into their potential in rooftop applications.

The estimation of energy yield in rooftop applications using bifacial PV modules is more challenging and less understood than for monofacial-based PV modules [17,18]. Several factors, including clearance height, module orientation and tilt angle, rooftop reflectance, and rear-side irradiance characteristics, affect the energy production of a bifacial PV module. The two methods that have been proposed to model the optical processes in such installations are the View Factor (VF) and Monte Carlo Ray Tracing (MCRT) models [19–29].

The need for accurate energy yield modelling for bifacial PV systems

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is highlighted by Raina and Sinha in their recent review article [17]. Their study emphasizes the need for optimizing the orientation of bifacial PV modules, highlighting the complexity of determining the optimal tilt compared to monofacial modules. Furthermore, the article suggests incorporating real-world factors such as array mismatch into simulation models to better comprehend the behaviour of bifacial modules under varying outdoor conditions. They conclude that accurate mathematical models should be developed and evaluated to assess performance in bifacial solar energy systems.

Many existing research studies concentrate on the precise modelling of bifacial systems within large-scale PV installations. To achieve the necessary level of precision, researchers have favoured the utilization of ray tracing [22,23,25,26,28,29]. These investigations primarily revolve around two types of systems: single-axis tracking systems and fixed tilt systems. Ray tracing has proven to be an indispensable tool in these endeavours.

For instance, Deline et al. observed that ray-tracing simulations were instrumental in studying edge brightening, which indicated a 15 %–25 % increase in rear irradiance at the ends of tracker rows. However, there was also up to a 20 % reduction in irradiance due to the presence of center-mounted torque tubes, causing multiple shadows [29]. McIntosh et al. showed that in a one-high configuration, nonuniform illumination led to a yield reduction of 0.23 % for a central module and 0.35 % for an edge module [26]. Zhao et al. conducted a comparative analysis between fixed tilt and single-axis tracking systems using a visual rendering software. They found that in fixed racking, the shading factor was significantly higher compared to the horizontal single axis tracking system [28]. Ernst et al. developed and validated a ray tracing model simulating bifacial illumination of utility-scale single-axis tracking systems and found that rear illumination of modules located deep in the system was affected by surrounding ground surface, highlighting the importance of considering edge effects [25].

In contrast, there are only limited studies available on the determination of the energy yield potential of bifacial PV modules in small-scale rooftop applications. The few existing studies have primarily relied on a simplified approach based on VF modelling [21,30–32], which has previously been shown to have limited accuracy in determining the rear illumination in bifacial PV [18,33–35]. The VF method relies on geometric parameters to determine how effectively one surface can “see” another surface. The use of VF-based models significantly simplifies the analysis by omitting structural components such as module frames and system mounting structures, assuming isotropic scattering for all considered surfaces and disregarding multiple reflections. Therefore, VF models may not fully capture the complexity of rooftop environments and lead to inaccurate estimation of the potential bifacial gain.

Nonetheless, Cha et al. proposed a VF modelling approach to estimate rear irradiance for bifacial photovoltaic modules in rooftop applications [30]. The authors conducted experiments with different albedos on individual modules and find that their model can predict the module power with a maximum error rate of 5 % and an average error of 1.84 % for plane of array irradiance exceeding 700 W/m². However, the average error masks significantly larger positive and negative errors, and the model’s accuracy diminishes greatly for irradiance values below this threshold. Additionally, the model does not resolve cell level irradiance, and thus local shading effects are not considered.

Mehadi et al. conducted a study on the energy yield of bifacial systems with different designs on a flat rooftop with 65 % albedo, using three VF modelling software: PVSOL, PVsyst, and System Advisor Model (SAM) [31]. They compared the energy yield of three system layouts: a vertical system mounted at the rooftop’s edge, a vertical system with east–west facing modules, and a system with tilted modules set at the optimal angle. The study estimates a 6.0 % energy yield gain for the tilted bifacial system compared to an unspecified monofacial system. The east–west facing bifacial system, according to their findings, achieves an average bifacial gain of 15.6 % based on the three modelling tools. However, the study reveals significant discrepancies in bifacial

gain predictions among the three modelling tools, with variations ranging from 35 % to 105 %. These differences highlight limitations and differences in the underlying VF models. Additionally, it should be noted that all systems in the study assume an unrealistic module height of 2 m above the mounting surface, which may not be practical for rooftop installations.

Mhaske et al. presented a case study that examined key parameters affecting the bifacial gain of photovoltaic systems using PVsyst [32]. This study focused on parameters that affect bifacial gains on the Effat University rooftop solar system, revealing that increasing the albedo can improve the gain by more than 3 %. Sensitivity analyses were conducted to evaluate the effect of module elevation on the gain, suggesting a diminishing gain beyond a specific elevation (0.6 m in the case study).

Desai et al. assessed the energy yield of mono- and bifacial PV systems [36]. This case study focused on a rooftop installation in Gujarat, India, comparing the technical and economic advantages of a 5-kW bifacial PV system with a 5 kW monofacial system. The modelled bifacial system generated over 8 % more energy annually than the monofacial system attributed to the rooftop’s high albedo, which results in a 2 to 13 % decrease in balance of system and space costs. However, the study’s limitations include the use of simplistic empirical equations for energy yield estimation, incomplete modelling inputs, and the absence of a View Factor model to estimate rear illumination. Consequently, the accuracy of the findings cannot be fully verified.

Accurately analysing the potential benefits of bifacial modules in rooftop scenarios, however, is critical for identifying and maximizing the potential for increased energy yield. Traditional modelling techniques such as VF modelling, are not well-suited to accurately estimate the potential bifacial gain in rooftop scenarios, due to the complexity and variability of optical effects present in these environments. Previous research has shown that VF modelling tends to underestimate rear-side illumination [34,35], and cannot entirely consider non-uniform illumination effects, such as from module frames and mounting components. In addition, VF modelling typically does not resolve effects at the edges of systems which is critical for the analysis of small rooftop systems.

The novelty of this research lies in its comprehensive approach to address several pivotal challenges inherent to modelling bifacial photovoltaic systems. The novel modelling framework couples MCRT simulations with a detailed electrical model of high-efficiency bifacial silicon PV modules, thereby tackling the limitations commonly associated with traditional VF modelling. Specifically, the approach resolves the complexities of real-world factors, including mismatch phenomena at both the cell-to-cell and array levels arising from non-uniform illumination effects and edge effects. Moreover, it meticulously accounts for non-uniform illumination effects stemming from module frames and mounting components, an aspect often overlooked in previous models. Additionally, the model uniquely resolves effects at the edges of systems, catering to the nuanced requirements of small rooftop installations.

This approach enables a more accurate quantitative analysis of the potential benefits of bifacial modules in rooftop applications than VF-based results reported so far. In particular, the impact of mounting components, module and system design, environmental conditions, and varying rooftop reflectivity on the bifacial energy yield gain are addressed, along with an analysis of the optimal tilt for rooftop-mounted monofacial and bifacial modules.

2. Methodology

This section will first introduce the modelling approach, the layout of the representative system in Caberra, Australia, and details the parameters analysed in this work.

2.1. Modelling approach

The PV system energy yield model employed in this work consists of four key steps:

Step 1: Optical Modelling.

In the first step, a detailed MCRT model is used to generate time-resolved illumination data for each individual half-cell within the modules. The modelling approach incorporated hourly satellite-based typical meteorological irradiance and weather data from PVGIS as its primary input source [37].

Step 2: Thermal Modelling.

Subsequently, the results derived from the optical model were integrated into thermal and electrical models. The estimation of cell temperature T_c was accomplished through the implementation of the PVSyst temperature model, as specified by Equation (1):

$$T_c = T_a + \frac{\alpha E(1 - \eta_m)}{U_c + U_v \times WS} \quad (1)$$

here, T_a represents the ambient temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), E denotes plane-of-array irradiance (W/m^2), α stands for the absorption coefficient, η_m represents the module efficiency, WS indicates the wind speed (m/s), U_c is the combined heat loss coefficient ($\frac{\text{W}/\text{m}^2}{\text{K}}$), and U_v the combined heat loss factor influenced by wind ($\frac{\text{W}/\text{m}^2}{\text{K}(\text{m}/\text{s})}$).

Step 3: Electrical Modelling.

The subsequent step involved the computation of the electrical power output of the PV system at each discrete time step. This calculation procedure accounted for cell-level irradiance and module-level temperature values and was executed utilizing the PVMismatch model [38].

Step 4: Integration

Finally, the electrical power output of the system is integrated over the full typical meteorological year.

The optical simulation is performed via energy partitioning MCRT where rays originating from the aperture plane of the scene are tracked until they escape, and the energy absorbed at each interaction is recorded. The MCRT model and time-resolved simulation approach is detailed in Ref. [25]. The MCRT model treats direct and diffuse light separately, and combines the results based on measured direct and diffuse irradiance values at each timestep. The diffuse sky is approximated with an isotropic distribution. Each object in the scene is defined by a geometry primitive and an optical manager that is in charge of calculating the locally absorbed energy and randomly generated

reflection/transmission directions. A dedicated PV module model was created for this work taking into account the interactions of light at all module layers and module frame. This PV module model was integrated into a comprehensive rooftop system model which encompassed not only the PV modules but also the entire house and its associated structural components within the MCRT framework. The cells are represented via a single bi-dimensional rectangular sheet with specific masking functions to deal with the inter cell gaps. The effective properties of the cells are introduced via custom-made optical managers able to consider texturing and other photovoltaic cell engineering related optical behaviours. This approach efficiently simplified the ray-tracing problem by avoiding the use of a large number of surfaces for each module.

2.2. System layout

In order to determine the advantages in energy yield from a bifacial rooftop-mounted module, a computational physical representation of a residential photovoltaic system was designed in the MCRT framework. The system consisted of two rows of eight solar modules each with a constant row-to-row distance of 5 m. The modules are tilt-rack mounted at a variable angle with the lower module edge positioned 20 cm above the surface of the roof. Adjacent modules are separated by a distance of 4 cm. As depicted in Fig. 1, the system is installed on a 23.0 m \times 12.4 m-sized, north-facing, 7.2 $^{\circ}$ pitched shed roof. There is an approximate 7.2 m setback from the roof edge on the eastern and western edges of the system, and depending on module tilt an approximate 2.8 m on the north and south sides. The roof is placed on a house in a unit-block of 17.5 m \times 35.5 m size. Furthermore, periodic boundary conditions place this house in a set of infinitely many identical houses.

We want to emphasize that the central objective of this paper is the development and comprehensive analysis of precise modelling for bifacial rooftop PV systems. While we do explore variations and enhancements in system design, including module tilt and electrical configuration, this aspect is within a limited scope and is secondary to our primary focus. It's important to note that our exploration of system design does not extend to considerations of module spacing or other design factors that influence optimal system performance.

The simulated photovoltaic modules each consisted of identical half-

Fig. 1. Illustration of the photovoltaic system on the pitched shed roof. The grey planes illustrate the periodic boundary conditions.

Table 1
Geometric and optical parameters of the simulated modules.

Parameter	Value
Cell length and width	166 mm
Wafer diameter	223 mm
Cell-to-cell gap	1 mm
Perimeter left/right	5 mm
Perimeter top/bottom	20 mm
Sub-module separation (cell row 12)	12 mm
Frame height	35 mm
Frame width	10 mm
Front-side frame lip	3.5 mm
Bracket width left/right	24 mm
Bracket width top/bottom	2.5 mm
Module glass front/rear	2 mm, Glass (Sodalime 0.05 wt% Fe ₂ O ₃ [41])
Glass ARC front/rear	110 nm, Glass ARC [42]
EVA front/rear	270 μm, UV transmissive [43]
Backsheet	R = 90 %, Lambertian
Frame/Bracket material	Material: Al, R = 0.75, Specularity = 0.5
Reflective coating	5 mm overlap of cell edges, R = 95 %, Lambertian

Fig. 2. Module layout of (a) monofacial with white backsheet, (b) bifacial with rear glass, and (c) bifacial with reflective coating.

cut solar cells made of 166 mm pseudo-square wafers sliced from a 223 mm diameter ingot and placed in an arrangement of 6 columns and 24 rows. Electrically, the 144-cells are connected in parallel substrings of each 72 half-cut cells at the top and bottom of the module. Three different module layouts were compared: (a) *Monofacial*, where the rear surface is a white backsheet with 90 % Lambertian reflectivity; (b) *Bifacial*, where the rear is a 2.0 mm thick glass with ARC; and (c) *BifacialCoated*: identical to the bifacial module, but an additional white reflective coating in the form of a localised grid is located on the inside of the rear glass sheet [39,40]. The rear glass coating is assumed to have a 95 % Lambertian reflectivity and overlaps the cell edges by 5 mm. Table 1 lists the common geometric parameters of the simulated modules and Fig. 2 illustrates the layout of the three variants.

As inputs to the thermal model, typical parameters for a freestanding mounting configuration [44] with $U_c = 29 \frac{W}{m^2 K}$ and $U_v = 0 \frac{W}{m^2 (m/s)}$ are assumed. Cell-irradiance values and cell temperature values are inputs

to the electrical model. The solar cells in the module are based on SunDrive Solar Pty Ltd 2021 silicon heterojunction cells. The certified properties of these cells include an efficiency of $\eta = (25.62 \pm 0.38) \%$, open-circuit voltage $V_{OC} = (746.2 \pm 3.1) mV$ and short-circuit current of $I_{SC} = (11061 \pm 120) mA$ with a cell area of $A = (274.4 \pm 1.1) cm^2$. In the module, this cell is represented by a two-diode model matching the experimental cell parameters. Fig. 3 shows the measured IV parameters and the corresponding two-diode fit. The electrical model is built on the PV Mismatch model [38] and considers the individual cell illumination, temperature and the electrical interconnection within each module and system. Lastly, the system power is integrated over the full year to compute the total energy yield.

3. Modelling results

Within this section, an extensive analysis and the results of critical parameters impacting the bifacial photovoltaic (PV) system's behaviour is presented. The parameters are systematically varied and thoroughly examined within the model, elucidating their individual and collective effects on system performance. The following section provides a detailed description of these parameters and the methodology employed for their analysis:

Module STC Performance – The module output power of the three PV modules (compare Fig. 2) is evaluated under Standard Test Conditions (STC) to establish a performance baseline.

MCRT Modelling Error – The required MCRT modelling accuracy is determined to achieve accurate results along the complete modelling chain.

Optimum Module Tilt – This analysis included a systematic variation of the tilt angles for monofacial and bifacial PV systems.

Weather Impact – The sensitivity of the PV system to varying weather conditions is assessed. Simulation results under clear-sky conditions and overcast conditions are compared.

Rooftop Reflectivity and Mounting Components – Rooftop reflectivity and the presence of mounting components can significantly affect system performance. In this analysis, various rooftop surfaces with different reflectivity properties are incorporated into the model. Additionally, the impact of mounting components on energy generation is examined. These analyses quantified the effects of rooftop properties and mounting configurations on system efficiency.

Electrical Optimization – Electrical optimization strategies are a focal point of the analysis. Two distinct approaches are compared: string-level and module-level electrical optimization. By varying these strategies and assessing their impact on electrical power output, valuable insights are gained into the most effective approach for maximizing energy generation.

Rooftop Specularity – The phenomenon of rooftop specularity is

Fig. 3. Cell current (a) and cell power (b) as function of cell voltage for the measured and modelled cells.

Table 2
Modelled STC power of the three module designs.

Parameter	Monofacial	Bifacial	BifacialCoated
Pmpp [W]	482.6	470.0	476.1
Pmpp rear [W]	–	415.9	353.7

Fig. 4. Normalised system power as function of MCRT simulation error.

explored to understand how specular reflections from the rooftop surface influence the energy yield of the bifacial PV system. Specularity parameters are systematically varied, and their effects on irradiance patterns are observed, providing a deeper understanding of this nuanced aspect of system performance.

The methodology involved systematically varying these parameters while monitoring the corresponding system metrics, including power output and energy yield. This comprehensive investigation yielded valuable insights into the behaviour of the bifacial PV system across diverse scenarios.

3.1. Module STC performance

The simulated power of the three module designs under standard testing conditions (STC), that is, at an irradiance level of 1000 W/m^2 , ambient temperature of $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and air mass AM1.5 g solar spectrum, is listed in Table 2. Due to a higher internal optical gain as a result of the rear reflector, the front side power of the monofacial module is approximately 2.7 % higher compared to the bifacial module. The bifacial module with reflective coating between the cell gaps can compensate for about half of this power loss on the front side, but at the cost of considerable power losses on the rear side.

3.2. MCRT modelling error

The Monte Carlo Ray Tracing (MCRT) method is effective in simulating photovoltaic system performance but requires an adequate number of “rays” to reduce statistical error and accurately determine system power in subsequent thermal and electrical models. This number of rays varies depending on the scenario, such as the sun position and the presence of shading effects. To enhance the simulation optimization process, the MCRT model calculates a statistical simulation error dynamically using ‘moving window statistics’ instead of employing a fixed number of rays. Further details regarding this approach can be found in the [Supplementary Information](#).

Two metrics are computed: the mean statistical simulation error across all individual solar cells in the system and the highest statistical simulation error among all cells. The MCRT simulation is terminated once a target simulation error is reached, with the latter being a stricter criterion as all cells must meet the target error.

To evaluate the impact of the statistical error on the simulated system power, 12 representative scenarios are simulated considering different sun position and light conditions. The system power is simulated for each scenario at varying statistical error targets, both for the mean and maximum error. Then, the relative system power is calculated from the average of the 12 scenarios normalised to the average with the highest number of rays (=smallest simulation error).

Fig. 4 illustrates the relative system power as a function of the target simulation error. At higher target simulation errors, the curves for maximum and mean errors diverge and gradually converge as the error decreases. It is observed that the relative system power reaches a saturation point at simulation error values below approximately 5–7 % for

Fig. 5. Specific energy yield for a Monofacial and a Bifacial system as a function of module tilt angle, for systems with individually optimized modules (left) and two parallel eight-module strings (right).

Fig. 6. (a) Absolute and (b) relative power of the 16-module Monofacial and Bifacial system configured in two parallel strings.

both the maximum and mean analysis. Consequently, subsequent MCRT simulations are conducted using a maximum simulation error of 3 % for all cells. This approach enables accurate prediction of photovoltaic system performance while minimizing computational resources.

3.3. Optimum module tilt

The specific energy yield (energy yield normalised to the nominal system power) was simulated for a monofacial system and a bifacial system. Initially, the upper limit of the bifacial energy yield gain was estimated by assuming no losses from module mounting components and a rooftop with 75 % reflectivity and 85 % Lambertian fraction (15 % specular). Such highly reflective rooftops are becoming more common, largely in order to minimize heat absorption from solar radiation through exposed roof surfaces. However, they also could play an important role in improving solar energy performance. Apart from the module bifaciality, the systems simulated were otherwise identical.

Fig. 5 shows the specific energy yield of both monofacial and bifacial systems as a function of module tilt. For the monofacial modules, the optimal inclination was found to be 35° , which aligns with the expected values for this latitude and weather pattern. Interestingly, the bifacial system exhibited a higher optimal tilt of 45° , indicating the significant influence of the rear contribution on the optimal system design. Notably, the bifacial system at a 45° tilt can achieve a remarkable increase in energy yield, up to 22.6 %, compared to the monofacial system at a 35° tilt.

Moreover, Fig. 5 provides a comparison between two system configurations: one with individually optimized modules, achieved through technologies such as DC optimizers or microinverters, and the other consisting of two parallel strings, each comprising of eight series-connected and thus group-optimized modules. In the simulated

scenario, the series-connected system demonstrates an impressive energy yield gain of 21.2 %. The individually optimized bifacial system achieves 22.6 % higher energy yield than the monofacial system.

3.4. Weather impact

To investigate the influence of clouds and time of day on the annual yield gain, the power output of the bifacial system was compared with the monofacial system under different weather conditions and throughout the course of two exemplary days. The different weather conditions result in a different impact of the direct and diffuse light simulated in the MCRT model.

Fig. 6 shows the power output data obtained from a clear-sky day and a partly cloudy day for both the monofacial and bifacial systems. Notably, the observations reveal a significant increase in the relative power output of the bifacial system, particularly during the morning and evening periods.

Throughout the day, the relative gain of the bifacial system remains reasonably steady. A notable observation is that the relative bifacial gain is nearly twice as high on the partly cloudy day compared to the clear-sky day. When considering a diffuse to global horizontal irradiance ratio above 60 % as “cloudy” for all time steps in the annual dataset, the cloudy days contribute approximately 28 % to the annual bifacial yield gain, despite accounting for only 15 % of the total monofacial annual yield. This indicates that cloud cover can significantly impact the annual yield gain of the bifacial system, and this effect is expected to be more prominent in cloudier environments.

3.5. Rooftop reflectivity and mounting components

Fig. 7 shows spectrophotometric measurements of BlueScope Steel

Fig. 7. Spectrophotometric measurements of selected COLORBOND® steel materials measured in 2022, with reflectivity values ranging from 25% to over 90%.

Fig. 8. Relative bifacial energy yield gain for systems with Monofacial, Bifacial and BifacialCoated modules, with and without mounting components, for modules with individual optimization (left) and modules configured in two parallel strings (right).

Table 3

Optimum tilt angle determined for the monofacial system and a bifacial system using *Bifacial* modules and mounting components and for each varied rooftop reflectivity.

Rooftop reflectivity (%)	Optimum tilt (°)	
	Monofacial system	Bifacial systems
30	35	35
50	35	40
75	35	45

COLORBOND® steel¹ materials showed reflectivity values ranging from 25 % to over 90 %. From these measurements broadband reflectivity values of 30 %, 50 % and 75 % were selected as examples of rooftops. Using these representative values, the bifacial gain was the bifacial gain was calculated, assuming 85 % Lambertian scattering (with 15 % specular reflection).

Fig. 8 shows the relative energy yield of systems again using the three different module types. The system configuration included mounting components comprising posts and vertical rafters that align with the module edges, along with two horizontal mounting rails positioned 30 cm from the top and bottom module edge. The impact of the mounting system arrangement on the output of the monofacial system was found to be negligible.

The optimal tilt angle was determined for each simulated rooftop reflectivity, with notable variations observed exclusively for the bifacial systems. While the tilt angles were adjusted in 5° increments during the

simulations, it is important to note that the exact optimum tilt angle may exist within a finer range and would require more detailed simulations. However, the influence of this fine-grained adjustment is expected to have minimal impact on the overall results. This can be observed in Fig. 5, where the energy yield exhibits a variation of less than 1 % within a ± 5° range around the maximum. Table 3 provides a summary of the corresponding optimum tilt angles for the studied scenarios.

Overall, the bifacial gain ranges from 5 % to 23 % across all the modelled cases and rooftop reflectivity. This highlights the considerable potential for energy yield enhancement offered by bifacial modules.

The mounting components cause a reduction in the bifacial gain potential ranging from 1 to 2 %. This suggests that the mounting components result in shading on the back of the module, potentially causing a mismatch in current within a single module. Consequently, this shading effect partially compromises the bifacial module’s ability to capture energy from the rear side. It is important to distinguish this shading effect from the module-to-module mismatch, which is evident when comparing the results of systems with individually optimized and string-connected modules. The module-to-module mismatch accounts for an additional up to 1.4 % reduction in the gain potential. Further details are discussed in the following Section 2.6.

Furthermore, the use of bifacial modules with an internal reflective coating leads to a reduction of over 2–4 % in the potential yield gain. This finding implies that while reflective coatings hold the potential to enhance the performance of bifacial modules in utility-scale PV systems [[9,10]], they do not provide the same level of benefit in scenarios where there is a significant contribution to energy yield from the rear side. Tables S1 and S2 list the specific yield and relative energy yield gain of all simulated scenarios.

¹ COLORBOND® and BlueScope are registered trademarks of BlueScope Steel Limited.

Fig. 9. Relative rear cell absorption for all modules in the *Bifacial* system for (a) morning, (b) noon, and (c) evening of a clear-sky day.

3.6. Electrical optimisation

As seen in the previous results in this paper, a comparison between string-level and module-level maximum power point tracking is important to consider when evaluating the performance of rooftop PV systems. There are specific factors which differentiate rooftop from utility-scale PV installations, such as the proximity of the modules to the roof surface and the higher reflectivity of the rooftop compared to the ground. These factors result in a significant impact on the rear illumination profile due to shading caused by the modules.

Fig. 9 illustrates the relative rear absorption of cells at different times of the day. Throughout the day, a consistent pattern emerges: the bottom half of the module experiences substantially lower rear illumination compared to the upper half. This observation is crucial, as many half-cell module designs employ two parallel substrings in the upper and lower sections of the physical module, similar to this study. The characteristic of the non-uniform illumination favours the use of these half-cell module designs when installed in a portrait orientation, as they are less susceptible

to mismatch between the two module sections. However, in landscape orientation, both substrings would be affected similarly by the non-uniform illumination, that would result in a reduced energy yield gain.

To assess the impact of this mismatch, simulations of a bifacial PV system without internal parallel connection of two substrings are conducted, while keeping the rest of the system and modules identical to those in the simulations depicted in Fig. 8. For a bifacial PV system with mounting components and 75 % reflective rooftop, a reduction in the bifacial gain of 0.9 % and 0.8 % for modules with individual optimization and modules configured in two parallel strings is observed, respectively.

Furthermore, the modules located at the edges of the system can receive significantly higher rear illumination, depending on the position of the sun and the time of day. This is especially relevant when considering module-to-module mismatch losses. When comparing the performance of string-level and module-level maximum power point tracking, it is observed that module-level tracking can achieve an increase of up to 1.4 % in the annual energy yield. Consequently, the utilization of module-level

Fig. 10. Specific energy yield of Bifacial PV systems with mounting components versus rooftop specularity using modules with individual optimization (red) and modules configured in two parallel strings (blue).

maximum power point tracking appears particularly advantageous in rooftop PV systems due to the specific shading patterns and varying rear illumination profiles experienced in this context.

Figures S1 and S2 show the relative front and total cell absorption for all modules in the system, highlighting that only a fraction of the rear contributes to the overall cell absorption. Figures S3 to S5 show the absolute front, rear and total cell absorption of each cell for the same three scenarios.

3.7. Rooftop specularity

In the preceding sections, simulations were based on the assumption that the reflection of rooftops exhibits an 85 % Lambertian fraction and 15 % specular fraction. However, it is important to acknowledge that certain rooftops may possess a higher degree of specularity. Consequently, the impact of varying rooftop specularity in a range from 15 % to 50 % was investigated for a constant reflectivity of 75 % and module tilt of 45°. Fig. 10 presents the specific energy yield of the bifacial system with mounting components as a function of specularity.

It is observed that altering the rooftop specularity, from the lowest to the highest value within the specified range, leads to a decrease in bifacial gain of up to 2.5 %. This decrease can be explained by the geometric relationship between the sun, the solar modules, and the roof surface. When the specular reflection component is higher, there is a lower probability that light traveling towards the roof surface will scatter onto the rear side of the modules. However, it is important to note that such high levels of specularity are unexpected, and it is anticipated that aging and surface roughening will decrease this factor by increasing scattering effects. Spectrophotometric measurements of COLORBOND® steel materials indicate a specular fraction of less than 10 %, as supported by the comparisons of measurements obtained with and without a specular reflectance port.

4. Discussion

In comparison to prior studies in the field of utility-scale PV installations [25,26,28,29], this research utilised ray tracing as a crucial tool to achieve the necessary simulation accuracy in the context of bifacial rooftop systems. In accordance with this previous research, this study also acknowledges the critical significance of ray tracing in attaining the level of precision.

Furthermore, a significant contribution of this work lies in the integration of a detailed electrical model to comprehensively account for the electrical impact stemming from non-uniform illumination. This is evident in the observed potential of a 1.4 % energy yield increase for

module-level optimized systems as opposed to string-level optimization.

Previous studies on bifacial rooftop systems used view factor (VF) modelling, which has known limitations. This study took a different approach, which has already been implemented successfully in the previous research in utility-scale PV. For instance, Cha et al. identified substantial simulation errors occurring under irradiance conditions of less than 700 W/m² [30].

Desai et al. previously reported an 8 % bifacial gain when compared to a monofacial rooftop system employing an empirical illumination model [36]. In contrast, this work demonstrated the feasibility of achieving bifacial gains exceeding 20 % in this context. This notable difference in results can be potentially attributed to the simplified assumptions made in the Desai study, which did not fully capture the complexities of rooftop applications.

Moreover, Mehadi et al. conducted a study on the potential bifacial rooftop energy yield gain that showcased significant variations in results stemming from different VF models [31]. These variations, even within their own study, made it challenging to directly compare their findings with this work. Their work suggested a 6 % bifacial yield gain for a tilted system assuming a 65 % rooftop reflectivity. In this study, under similar rooftop reflectivity conditions, the system would achieve a bifacial gain of approximately 17 %, as inferred from the results presented in Fig. 8. The differences between the findings in this work and Mehadi et al.'s can be attributed in part to variations in system layout. While the rooftop system in this work provided a modest amount of reflective surface around the modules and optimized the tilt angle separately for monofacial and bifacial systems, Mehadi et al. assumed a constant tilt angle for both systems, optimized for the monofacial configuration. Additionally, they positioned some modules right at the edge of the flat rooftop, limiting the amount of light reflected onto the rear of the panels. In addition, the difference in location between this study and Mehadi's analysis affects the accessible solar resource and is therefore expected to affect the achievable bifacial gain.

Mhaske et al. generally concluded with the importance of albedo in influencing bifacial gain, a conclusion also supported by the current work [32]. However, Mhaske et al. reported only a 3.2 % improvement in gain for a 45 % absolute increase in rooftop reflectivity, while the findings in this study suggest a substantial 12.1 % additional bifacial gain, considering a detailed system with mounting. Once again, these disparities can be attributed to differences in system design. Mhaske et al. assumed a constant tilt angle of 15° for both their bifacial and monofacial systems, optimized for the monofacial configuration. Furthermore, they utilized a small module pitch of 1.4 m, which limited the amount of reflected light available to the module rear from the roof. Despite these differences in system design, a critical takeaway from this work is the necessity to optimize the tilt angle separately for bifacial modules, as it cannot be assumed to be identical to that of monofacial systems. Similar to Mehadi's study, differences in the locations of the systems outlined in Mhaske's study and this research have different effects on the available solar resource, and consequently are expected to have an effect on the achievable bifacial gain.

To put these findings into a broader perspective, bifacial modules require installation and maintenance cost nearly identical to monofacial modules, and a small to negligible capital cost increase [45]. The more than 20 % yield gain identified in this work would either lead to significant cost and installation footprint reductions or a significant economic gain over an equivalent monofacial system. This yield gain surpasses the typical range of 4 %–15 % achieved by utility-scale solar farms, which varies depending on the module type and ground albedo [29,46]. Similar to ground-mounted PV systems, the results in this study show that bifacial systems yield gains are higher with highly reflective roof materials. However, in a rooftop context, such highly-reflective cool roof materials provide additional benefits to the building energy consumption and are already economically profitable in areas where there is significant cooling demand in summer [10,47]. Rooftop PV modules systems have been shown to reduce building temperatures

independently [48,49]. The encouraging yield gains presented in this work indicate that a deeper analysis of the techno-economic synergy between reflective roof materials and rooftop bifacial module systems could result in simultaneous economical electricity production and reduction of cooling energy needs in building.

5. Conclusion

This study employed MCRT coupled with a detailed electrical model to assess the potential gains provided by bifacial PV modules over traditional monofacial ones. This comparison was performed using a full rooftop representative PV system in Canberra, Australia. The results indicate that the use of bifacial modules rooftop PV systems can result in an energy yield gain of up to 22.6 % compared with monofacial systems. Rooftop reflectivity was shown to have the most significant impact on the bifacial yield gain potential of systems.

Additionally, the investigation revealed that rooftop reflectivity also influences the optimal tilt angle for bifacial modules. Compared to monofacial modules, bifacial modules exhibit higher optimal tilt angles for maximum energy generation. Importantly, the optimal tilt angle increases with rooftop reflectivity, underscoring the significance of tailoring the system design to the specific roof conditions to achieve optimal performance.

Furthermore, the study highlights the significant implications of system and module design when utilizing bifacial modules in rooftop systems. At the module level, it is found that the parallel interconnection of a top and bottom substring is crucial for achieving high yield gains. Without parallel substrings, bifacial gain was reduced by 0.9 % for a system with mounting components at a 75 % reflective rooftop. Moreover, it is essential to prioritize high bifaciality over design choices that prioritize maximizing front module power at the expense of rear power generation, due to rooftop reflectivity values exceeding albedo values typically encountered in utility-scale PV installations.

Moreover, the study identifies an additional avenue for enhancing energy yield by incorporating individual module-level optimizers. These optimizers take advantage of the observed increased rear illumination patterns at the edges of bifacial systems. By optimizing the performance of each module individually, the overall energy generation potential of bifacial technology can be further improved by up to 1.4 %. This finding emphasizes the importance of considering not only system and module design but also the implementation of advanced optimization strategies to maximize the benefits of bifacial modules in rooftop applications.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

M. Ernst: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **X. Liu:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **C.-A. Asselineau:** Software, Writing – review & editing. **D. Chen:** Conceptualization, Resources, Writing – review & editing. **C. Huang:** Resources, Writing – review & editing. **A. Lennon:** Conceptualization, Resources, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2023.117947>.

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